

Popular Article

Wonder Drug- Aspirin: 125 years of acetylsalicylic acid (ASA)

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Abstract

Aspirin, a well-known, mostly widely used and cheapest anti-inflammatory drug completed 125th year of its discovery. Besides its analgesic, antipyretic property, its daily use is recommended to lower the risk of heart attack, clot-related strokes and other blood flow problems in patients who have cardiovascular disease or who have already had a heart attack or stroke. Aspirin is over the counter medicine (OTC) and its drug facts label recommends aspirin for relieving headache, pain, swelling, or fever. However, drug label does not have information for using aspirin to lower the risk of heart attack and clot-related strokes. In such case, we need to take advice from our medical practitioner. Current article is written to commemorate the aspirin on account of its fabulous role to lower the risk of heart attack, clot-related strokes and other blood flow problems in patients and to address the concern raised by scientist about the risk of side effects in millions of people taking a daily aspirin without physician supervision and without an actual diagnosis of cardiovascular disease.

Introduction

Aspirin, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, is one of the most widely used medication globally and cheapest drug in medicine. It is on the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines (WHO, 2021). It possesses analgesic, antipyretic, and antiplatelet properties, and are used to reduce pain, fever, and/or inflammation. It is also indicated in pregnant women who are at high risk of preeclampsia (PE) and antiphospholipid syndrome (APS) (Cadavid, 2017). Its role in cancer prevention emerged since its use in cancer was first hypothesised in the early 1990s (Rosenburg, 1990) and has continued to grow over the following three decades (Zhang, 2021).

Discovery of Aspirin: Year 2022, celebrates the 125th anniversary of acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), the active ingredient that brought Aspirin to fame (Bayer.com). The fascinating history of aspirin-like remedies traces back to antiquity. Aspirin has come a long way since the use of willow bark by the ancient Sumerians and Egyptians to wonder drug. Willow bark has been used by Sumerians and Egyptians as a traditional medicine for more than 3500 years for its pain reliever and antipyretic properties. In 1838, the Italian chemist, Raffaele Piria discovered the active ingredient in willow bark—salicylic acid (Marson and Pasero, 2006). 60 years later, on August 10, 1897, Dr. Felix Hoffmann, a Bayer chemist, in a lab in Wuppertal-Elberfeld, Germany discovered and synthesized the first chemically pure and stable form of acetylsalicylic acid and trademarked as aspirin by Bayer AG in 1899 (Bayer.com). Aspirin comes from “acetyl” and Spirsäure, a German name for salicylic acid. Aspirin differed markedly from previous forms of salicylic acid, with improved tolerability and reduced gastrointestinal side effects, and remains widely used as both an anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic drug. In 1969, the round tablet made its way to the moon with the astronauts in the Apollo 11 capsule (Bayer.com). Highlighting the significant role of aspirin, Thore Grimm, Head of the Bayer Corporate Archives wrote that “The young Hoffmann could not have imagined that this substance would become the 20th century’s most common active ingredient for therapeutic use, and that it is still just as important even now, as new effects and areas of application are discovered.” (Bayer.com).

Mechanism of Action of Aspirin: Although aspirin is a NSAID, it differs from other NSAIDs in having additional antiplatelet action exerted through irreversible inhibition of cyclooxygenase enzyme (COX-1), while others are reversible one. Irreversible inhibition of platelet cyclooxygenase enzyme (COX-1) and ultimately of prostaglandin synthesis (Vane, 1971), was the main mechanism discovered by Sir John Vane, a British pharmacologist, in 1971 and this stimulated a new era of aspirin usage. Sir John Vane was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1982 along with Sune Bergström and Bengt Samuelsson for "their discoveries concerning prostaglandins and related biologically active substances". (Nobelprize.org). Subsequent clinical and experimental studies have demonstrated that low-dose aspirin irreversibly acetylates a serine residue at position 530 on the cyclooxygenase-1 (COX-1) enzyme in platelets, thus blocking synthesis of prostaglandin G₂/H₂ (Fig. 1). It is the first reaction in a series that allows transformation of arachidonic acid into the potent platelet agonist, thromboxane A₂. This anti platelet was found effective in patients with coronary artery disease and stroke. In addition, it has number of pleiotropic effects like suppression of acute phase reactants and subclinical inflammation, stimulation of NO synthesis, immunomodulatory effect on activated macrophages and lymphocytes. The mechanism of action is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Inhibition of Platelet Thromboxane A₂ Pathways by Low-Dose Aspirin (Taken from- Gasparayan et al., 2008)

Aspirin setbacks and related side effects: Aspirin went through a number of obstacles over the period following its discovery. Gastritis associated with aspirin use became evident with the discovery of gastroscope in 1932 (Douthwaite, 1938; Douthwaite & Lintott, 1938). This paved the way for the development of paracetamol in 1956 and ibuprofen in 1962, further declining the aspirin's popularity. Acute encephalopathy and fatty infiltration of the viscera in children occurring in Reye syndrome, was also found to be associated with aspirin (Mortimer, 1962), leading to prohibition on the use of aspirin below the age of 16 years, except in Kawasaki disease. Thinning of the blood due to anti platelet activity and gastric bleeding due to inhibition of cytoprotective prostaglandin synthesis are the other potential side effects.

Current confusion over the use of aspirin: Being the over-the-counter drug, we can use aspirin in pain and fever. But one needs to be cautious while using low dose aspirin for prolonged use especially in case of cardiovascular problems. Aspirin has long been and continues to be considered the first line, gold standard doctor-directed treatment for the prevention of having another heart attack or ischemic (clot-related) stroke (Bayer.com). In this regard, the United States Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recently updated their draft guidelines recommendations to refine who should be taking low-dose aspirin. In line with this, recently a report was published USA today newspaper on the topic "Why you should reconsider taking daily aspirin" (usatoday.com). All these things reaffirmed that aspirin is not appropriate for everyone in relation to start, stop or modify an aspirin regimen, without advice from healthcare professional. This move was taken on account of reports stating increased risks of heart attack by 63 percent and by 40 percent for a clot-related stroke after discontinuing an aspirin regimen. The overall objective was to have rational and effective use of aspirin as its fabulous mechanism of action and to outweigh benefit when compared with side effects.

Conclusion

The fascinating mechanism of action and greater tolerance by patients make aspirin most commonly prescribed drug for prevention of atherothrombotic events. In addition, it has number of pleiotropic effects like suppression of acute phase reactants and subclinical inflammation, stimulation of NO synthesis, immunomodulatory effect on activated macrophages and lymphocytes. It also potentiates the action of other antiplatelet agents (such as clopidogrel, dipyridamole, cilostazol) in the case of combined therapy. All these facts make it worth celebrating 125th anniversary of aspirin and is likely to remain the cornerstone of antiplatelet therapy for long-term cardiovascular

prevention.

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